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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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AN EXPOSITION OF CIVIL AND CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE

By

Adamu Idris Tanimu*, Habila Isah Barau**, Muhammed Adamu Muhammed***

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ABSTRACT

This article is aimed at explaining medical negligence, as well as explain the type of liability involve, that is to say what negligence constitutes and attracts either Civil or Criminal liability. The article will also highlight the degree of negligence, its, types, and also what acts amount to medical negligence on the part of a Doctor, a Nurse and other hospital staff. The researcher adopted the doctrinal legal research which is purely qualitative. Online-based resources were gathered and analyzed using the traditional approach of researching into law as it stands against technological realities. The article will also highlight the duties of a Doctor, duty of care he owes his patients, adequate compensation available to the victim as well as the liabilities attached to the Doctor's actions or inactions.

Keywords: Civil, Criminal, Liability, Medical and Negligence.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Human civilization has gone beyond self-help in resolving misgivings or wrongs done by fellow human beings to one another.¹ Conflict which has long been an inevitable aspect of human existence (be it human against human or human against nature)² attracts legal responses which have proven that fiduciary principles are capable of protecting not only narrow legal and economic interest but also serve to defend

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¹ J.A. Madden, 1978, Journal of Hellenic Studies, 160-161.

²www.Haines Center.com. (accessed, 20 Nov, 2020).

fundamental human and personal interest³. Legal responses which have evolved over the years has been designed to provide redress for wrongs and wrong doing perpetrated by members of the society against one another⁴.

Furthermore, torts are legal or civil wrongs committed against people or organizations causing them loss⁵. Certain actions are treated as legal wrongs, under the law of torts. Where a conduct is tagged as a legal wrong, the injured person has a right of action for redress against the wrong doer before a court of law.⁶

Civil and criminal liability for medical negligence may be attributed to a doctor or a hospital when any of their actions, omissions or failure to act causes injuries to a patient; it may also be the hospital's liability when the damage is caused by negligence of its staff (doctors another personal). The rules that govern the civil and criminal liability and the way of compensating the damages are different due to the grounds on which the doctor performs medical services and, in case of hospital's liability, the relationship between doctor and health institution.

This article undertakes an examination of tort law and the various elements that constitute the civil wrong. This is essential because of the fact that negligence which is the focus of this article is parented by torts. It will further narrow its examination of negligence to the article focus that is, medical negligence and will traverse the various principle that the court considers in attempting to find negligence on the part of the doctor; thus, principles of causation, remoteness of damages, amongst others as well as *Bolam* and *Bollitho* principles are examined.

2.0 LEGAL FRAME WORK OF MEDICIAL NEGLINGE VS NEGLIGENCE

a. TORTS LAW

The word tort 'tort' is derived from the Latin word "*tortus*" meaning 'twisted⁷'. It came to mean 'wrong' and is still so used in French: 'J'ai tort; meaning 'I am wrong'. It found its way into English through Norman French where it acquired the meaning 'wrong'. Today, it refers to a wrongful act or omissions that result in civil liability to an injured

³ Emiri F.O Medical Law and Ethics in Nigeria (Lagos:Malthouse PressLtd2012)270-271

⁴ Ibid 271

⁵ See Williams Spaulding <http://thismatter.com/moneyinsurance/legal-liability.htm>(accessed24thoctober,2019)

⁶ Goidberg J C p and Zippursky B C" Civil Recourse Defended: A reply to posner,Calabresi,Rustad,Chamallas and Robiniette" (2003) Indiana Law Journal Vol.88:569,569-609.

⁷ Lundmark T. Common Law Torts& Contract (Volume 1 of juristische Arbeitsbucher) (Lit Ver Lag Munster:1998) 1-3

person by the tortuous act of the wrong doer⁸. In English, the word ‘tort’ has a purely technical, legal meaning—a legal wrong for which the law provides a remedy⁹. The word “tort” has been defined in various ways by various jurists and authors. It is difficult to arrive at satisfactory all-embracing definition. Each writer has different formulation and admits that their definition is unsatisfactory¹⁰. Winfield describes tort as breach of duty primarily fixed by law; this duty is towards persons generally and its breach is redressed by an action for unliquidated damages.¹¹

b. THE LAW RELATING TO NEGLIGENCE

Negligence is a relative newcomer to the law of torts¹². What this means is that “negligence” is a mental element in tortious liability. In ordinary language, negligence could be described as carelessness. But in strict legal analysis, negligence means more than heedless or careless conduct whether in omission or commission: it properly connotes the complex concept of duty, breach and damage there by suffered by the person to whom the duty is owed¹³. Lord Alderson B also defines negligence as the omission to do something that a reasonable man, guided upon those considerations that ordinarily regulate the conduct of human affairs would do or as doing something that a prudent and reasonable would not do¹⁴. Negligence is generally described as behavior that creates unreasonable foreseeable risks of injury,¹⁵ a breach of a legal duty to take care that results in damage to the claimant.¹⁶ It is a fault-based tort and to be successful in an action, a claimant must prove certain elements, namely:

- I) that the defendant owes the claimant a duty to take care
- II) that the defendant had breach that duty
- III) that damages or injury results to claimant as a result of the conduct or misconduct of the defendant.¹⁷

⁸ Harp wood VH Modern Tort (17thed) (Routledge Cavendish: 2009) 1.

⁹ The Pottery Glass Salesman (3) O Gorman Publishing Company: New York (2011) 1

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Winfield and Jolowic on Torts, (17thed) (Thomson Sweet & Maxwell: London 2006) 5

¹² Underwood P “Negligence & Forceseability: Doctrine of Law or Public policy” (1999) This paper was first presented at the Australian Insurance Law Association National Conference, Hobart 4 -6 August. <http://www.supremecourt.tas.gov.au/data/assent/pdfile/0003/53760/Negilegence99.pdf> (Accessed 20th Nov, 2019).

¹³ Per Lord Wright in Lochgelly Iron and Coal Co V M’ Mullan (1934) AC 1 at 25.

¹⁴ Blyth V Birmingham Waterworks Co. (1856) 11 Exch. 781 at 784.

¹⁵ Wright R W “The Standard of Care in Negligence Law” in David G Owen (ed) Philosophical Foundations of Tort Law (Oxford University Press: 2001) 250

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ Except where the doctrine of res ipsa loquitur applies. Scott v. London & St. Katherine Docks (1865) 159 er 665.

3.0 ELEMENTS OF NEGLIGENCE RELATING TO MEDICAL SERVICES

(a) Duty of Care

Whether or not a duty of care exists between parties is a question of law¹⁸. A man is entitled to be as negligent as he please to the whole world if he owes no duty of care.¹⁹ The courts in the case of *Donoghue V Stevenson*,²⁰ formulated the general criteria for the existence of the proximity that would give rise to the duty of care. **Lord Atkin** stated that it is remarkable how difficult it is to find in the English authorities statements of general application defining the relationship between parties that gives rise to duty.

Liability here is not without borders; a man can only be expected to pay for those harms which a reasonable man in his shoes can reasonably foresee. This is why the principle of foresee ability of the risk of harm is relevant to answering the question of whether the defendant can reasonably be expected to have taken any precaution?²¹ It would be unfair to impose liability on a person for failure to take precaution against a risk of which they had neither knowledge nor means of knowledge.²²

(b) Breach of Duty

The defendant who must have breached the duty he owed and this is usually a matter of fact for the courts to decide. The standard of care expected of a person is the standard of care involves must be proportional to the degree of risk involved.²³ Negligence is essentially concerned with compensating people who have suffered damage as a result of the carelessness of others. If a duty of care cannot be established and shown exist in each of the situations concerned, then the remaining elements of the tort of negligence need not recognized. For the court to hold that a breach had occurred, there should be presence of 'causation' which is the link between the defendant's negligence and the damage suffered by the claimant. Essentially the damage or loss must result from the defendant's breach of duty.

(c) Damages

¹⁸ Ibid at 132-135

¹⁹ See also *Aclock v Chief Constable of South Yorkshire* (1991) 3 WLR 1057 HL

²⁰ (1932) AC 562.

²¹ Law of Negligence Review "Foreseeability, Standard of Care, Causation and Remoteness of Damage: Law of Negligence Review" 101-119. <http://revofneg.treasury.gov.au/Report2/PDF/Foreseeability>. Pdf (accessed 1 august, 2019)

²² *ibid*

²³ Lord Wright in *Northwestern Utilities Ltd v London Guarantee & Accident Co Ltd.*, intelligence, knowledge, skill etc, are all parameters the court will use to measure a reasonable man.

It is trite law that damage is the gist of the action in negligence.²⁴ The scope of actionable damages includes property, personal mental and pure economic loss.²⁵ Injuries must be actual compensation; no cause of action accrues unless there is damage. But the issues annexed to this element of negligence are what constitute damage. There seems to be point of disagreement that the claimant must suffer injury before he can safely come under tort of negligence; the cause of divergent views is what actually constitutes the “injury”.

4.0 MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE

The facts are often in the same line a patient has suffered harm as a result of action or inaction of a Doctor. The question that follows is, ‘what are the legal remedies available to the patient?’ often times expression such as ‘Medical Negligence’, ‘Medical Malpractice’, ‘infamous conduct’, ‘Gross Misconduct’ are used interchangeably or without accurate knowledge about the scope limits and implications of each.

When the term ‘negligence’ is mentioned, it simply connotes failure to exercise the care that a reasonable prudent person would exercise in like circumstance. But, ‘malpractice’ denotes a type of negligence where a licensed professional fails to provide services as per standards set by a regulatory body; a negligent action could either be intentional or simply a reckless act. Under malpractice there is always the presence of intentions. However, the criteria for proving both are often similar, that is, duty, breach of duty, causation and damages.²⁶

The Medical and Dental Practitioners Act Cap 221²⁷ uses the expression ‘misbehave’²⁸ and “infamous conduct” to explain the instances where the medical and Dental Investigate the conduct of a medical practitioner that it considers inimical to the law.²⁹ The expression used above (that is, ‘misbehave’ and infamous conduct’) have not been defined by the same Act,³⁰ which created them. *Ayoola JSC* pointed out in the case of *Medical and Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Tribunal v Okonkwo*³¹ that it is difficult

²⁴ Makwe v. Nwukor (2016)14 NWLR(pt733)1

²⁵ Kodinllye G. Nigerian Law of Torts (Spectrum: Ibadan 1995)7-8.

²⁶ Yakubu J.A. Medical Law in Nigeria (Demyaxs law Books: Ibadan 2002)42.

²⁷ Laws of federation of Nigeria 2004 Cap8.

²⁸ Section 15(1)

²⁹ Section 16(1)

³⁰ Medical and Dental Practitioners Act 2004 Cap8.

³¹ (2001)19 WRN1

to determine the precise meaning of this expression.³² In the case of *Sloan v General Medical Council*³³, Lord Guest opined also that there are no closed categories of infamous conduct and in every case it must be a question for the committee to decide first whether the facts alleged have been proved and second whether or whether or Dental Practitioner was in relation to those facts guilty of infamous conduct in a professional respect.³⁴

a. Duty of Care in Medical Negligence

A doctor owes the patient a duty of care.³⁵ When a man holds himself out of another man that he possesses special knowledge and skill and on basis another man consults him for healing then the law recognizes that he owes a duty to that patient.³⁶ According to *pattison*, such duties will arise when there is foresee ability of damage, sufficient proximity between the parties and it was just and reasonable to impose a duty of care.³⁷ But, once a doctor takes responsibility for treating patient then such duty to assist is established³⁸.

In *NBN LTD V TASA LTD*³⁹, the Court of Appeal discussed the standard required for the existence of contributory negligence. According to the Court:

The standard of care in contributory negligence is what is reasonable in the circumstance and this in most case corresponds to the standard of care of negligence. Although contributory negligence does not depend on foreseeability.

The existence of a duty to take care towards patient reposing in the Health care practitioner. A breach of that duty by the health care practitioner;⁴⁰. The breach of the health care practitioner's duty caused damage to the patient. The type of damage caused was reasonably foreseen.⁴¹

Under common law a doctor can be held liable for damages resulting from his failure to exercise the reasonable and ordinary care, diligence, and skill in the diagnosis and

³² Dada J A. Legal Aspect of Medical Practice in Nigeria (Optimistpress Calabar :2013)103-105

³³ (1970)2 All ER686 at688.

³⁴ Yakubu(n25)36-37

³⁵ Ogwuche S A (ed) Compendium of Medical Law(Maiyati Chambers: Lagos)1

³⁶ "figuring foreseeability"<http://tortssymposium.lawwfu.edu/papers/owen.pdf> (accessed 11th August,2020)

³⁷ Barret v Ministry of Defence (1995)3 AllE.R.

³⁸ Ogwuche (34)55

³⁹ (1996)8 NWLR(pt468)511

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Ibid.

treatment of his patients which other doctors engage in the same line of practice during the same period of time ordinarily possess and exercise⁴².

b. Duties of a medical Doctor

In the case of **Pike v Honsinger**⁴³ the court stated that a doctor and surgeon by taking charge of a case impliedly represents that he possesses and the law places upon him the duty of possessing that reasonable degree of learning and skill that is ordinarily possessed by doctors and surgeons in the locality where he practices and which is ordinarily regarded by those conversant with the employment as necessary to qualify him to engage in the business of practicing medicine and surgery. Upon consenting to treat a patient, it becomes his duty to use reasonable care and diligence in the exercise of his skill and the application of his learning accomplish the purpose for which he was employed. He is under the further obligation to use his best judgment in exercising his skill and applying his knowledge.⁴⁴

The implication of the above is that three things are required of the average doctor, and these will be examined briefly. The first is that, he must possess that reasonable degree of learning and skill that ordinarily possessed by an average doctor or surgeon in the locality where he practices as necessary to qualify him in practicing medicine and surgery.⁴⁵ But in instances where a doctor holds himself out as possessing a special skill or as being versed in an area of medicine the “ordinarily” and “reasonable” rule will not avail him. If a specialist possessed greater skill in the line of his specialty than the average doctor, there would be no reason to employ him specialist or for the attendant honour and pecuniary gains of someone possessing such additional skill. It then behooves on such a “specialist” or it becomes a duty on him to give his patients benefit of such skill.⁴⁶

The second requirements that the doctor is ‘under the further obligation to his best judgment, not his guess or hasty surmise, not his snap judgment but his best interest.⁴⁷ Professionals usually take ranks in proportion to their possession of this faculty.

⁴² See also Report of the Special definitions of Medical Malpractice, State of New York (1976) 170-72.

⁴³ Ibid 155 N.Y 201.

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ See *Carpenter v Bloke*, 75 N.Y. 12.

⁴⁶ *Baker v Hancock*, 29 Ind. 456, 63 N.E 323.

⁴⁷ *Strykes Lp Courts and Doctors* (Macmillan Company: New York 1932) 9

However, in using his 'best judgment' the doctor should not depart from the duty he owes his patient or depart from the following the approved methods in general use. The third is that the doctor or surgeon must keep abreast of the times and must follow the 'Approved methods in general use'.⁴⁸ The terms 'standard Medical Practice' and 'Acceptable Medical Practice' often used interchangeably. Although scholars have contended that the word 'standard' ordinarily conveys the impression that medical practice is standardized, fixed or non-changing, this is not actually the case.⁴⁹ Therefore, every doctor to utilize the fresh ideas acquired in medical and scientific journals, text books, lectures courses, and meetings/ conferences organized by state medical societies, where he can meet more experienced doctors.⁵⁰

c. Breach of Duty in Medical Negligence

It is every accident, mistake or mishap in medical parlance that the law will tag as medical negligence. A patient must prove that the defendant doctor has failed to meet the standard of a reasonable competent professional with the relevant skill. Therefore, a doctor must meet the standards of reasonable competent doctor, while a specialist who has move beyond the level of an ordinary doctor must equally meet the standards set and expected such specialist.

According to *Pattinson*,⁵¹ the standard of care is a question of law and its application to the evidence, a question of fact. The two that is, law and facts, merge when the standard of care is mapped against the facts of specific cases. Ordinarily, under negligence simpliciter, the standard of care expected is that of a reasonable man, that is, the care that a reasonable man would show in the circumstances under consideration; this is amount of care expected of an ordinary prudent man in the given circumstances.⁵² A reasonable man in context of the law is a person with normal intelligence and average knowledge of every life,⁵³ and the court usually considers the intelligence, knowledge and skill of the defendant in deciding who to describe as 'a reasonable man'.⁵⁴

⁴⁸ Kimmel M. 'Legal Remedies for Medical Errors, A guide to the Law of medical practice and Malpractice(2nd ed)(New York Central Book company: Brooklyn1970)

⁴⁹ Ibid.

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ *Pattinson* (n)7

⁵² *Bolton v Stone* (1951) HL

⁵³ *Idid* 229.

⁵⁴ *Philips vWhiteley* (1938)1 All Er 566;.

d. Damage or Loss Resulted from the Breach in Medical Negligence

A patient cannot find respite in court if he establishes the two issues mentioned above but fails to prove that he suffered an amount of damage or injury as a result of the doctor's negligence. It is also a difficult area to establish in court as a lot of factors may account for the damage. In some situations, the sets of evidence will simply go against the claimant⁵⁵. In essence, causations and remoteness of damage in medical negligence seem highly difficult to establish in court. In the case of ***Wilsher v Essex AHA***,⁵⁶ baby who was born pre-maturely was negligent administer over dose of oxygen; this resulted in a medical condition known as retrolental fibroplasias, which mean total blindness in one eye and partial vision in the other. When the matter came up before trial court the problem of establishing damages was greatly impaired because of condition. The position of the trial judge which was the defendant needs to show that their negligent act was responsible for the injury was over ruled by the House of Lords who held that the onus of proving causation rested with the claimant. The Appeal Court thus ordered a retrial and asked the claimant to prove negligent act of the doctor was material contribution to his injury. This makes it clear that it mostly takes one doctor to nail another.

5.0 BOLAM PRINCIPLE VS MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE

The plaintiff in this case, **Mr John Bolam**, was a psychiatric patient who was suffering from clinical depression. He was advised to go for a treatment known as Elector-Convulsive Therapy (E.C.T) by Dr. de *bastarreacha*, a consultant psychiatrist, at freirn Hospital. This form of treatment involves passing an electric current through the patient's brain induced a fit. Certainly this form of treatment was novel in the 1950s; therefore doctors differed in opinion as to how best to minimize the risk of the patient suffering bone fracture during the fit⁵⁷. Although he was given a 'consent' from, which he duly signed, he was not alerted of the risk of fracture, that could occur because of the fit or convulsions that such treatment might induce. In the hospital where **Mr. Bolam** was treated, a manual restrain was being used that required the nurses to hold to the patient down by the chin. Further, after his

⁵⁵ See also the case of *Barnet, and Robision v Post Office* (1974) 1 WLR.1176.

⁵⁶ (1988)AC.107.

⁵⁷ *Bolam v Frien Hospital Management Committee* (1957)1 WLRat 589-593.

treatment he was not given any relaxant drugs; consequently, he suffered several injuries such as serious pelvic injuries and dislocation of hip joints. This was caused by the femur on both sides being driven through the cup of pelvis. The plaintiff thus maintained an action in negligence.⁵⁸ In his claim, he maintained that the doctor was negligent in not giving him a relaxant drug and in failing to provide adequate physical restraints to prevent the injuries he sustained. He admitted being given the consent form but argued that the failed to warn him of the risks involved in the treatment⁵⁹. Consequently, the is difficult to establish that a doctor breached the duty of care. The **Bolam** principle insists upon a negligence test that is unique only to medical profession as the standard of care is “set by other doctors”.⁶⁰ Because it will be insufficient to call expert witness to testify that the defendant ought not to have acted or carried out the procedure in the way and manner he did, the plaintiff must further adduced that no “responsible body of medical opinion “ would have approved of acting in that way. This appears very difficult because the defendant can simply show through his own acknowledge expert witness that the defendant dealt with patient was within the range of acceptable practice.⁶¹ The doctor would thus not liable or negligent even if it is shown that the doctor made a misdiagnosis⁶² or failed to inform the patient about an alternative treatment that was available so far evidence can be brought to show that the doctor has acted within “approved” conduct by a “responsible body of medical opinion.”⁶³

5.1 The Operational Effect of Bolam Principle.⁶⁴

A doctor is to be judged on the state of knowledge at the time of the incident. If at the time of the occurrence the state of knowledge supports the procedure or type of treatment, then the doctor will not be held negligent.⁶⁵ It has been said that this is too judged based on the standard of the day rather than with the benefit of hindsight⁶⁶. A doctor is not to be expected to have read or digested all available material information

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ In Garwood-Gower, A Whaet K and Tingle(eds) Health care Law and Ethicd (Elsevier Limited:England 2005)

⁶¹ Herring J. Medical Law and Ethics (5thed)(Oxford University Press: New York 2014)41-43.

⁶² Thompson V Blake-James (1998) Lloyd’s RepMed 187.

⁶³ Ibid.42-43.

⁶⁴ Ibid. See also Roe v Minister of Health (1954)2 A1ER 131.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

or research in that area of treatment or ailment which has only become available. Thus, it was held that a doctor was not negligent because he had failed to read an article published six months earlier in a medical journal;⁶⁷ nor was doctor negligent for failing to use newly invented equipment that was not widely available.⁶⁸ The acceptability of the types of treatment or procedure needs not be by a substantial body of opinion; all that is required is for the defendant to show that his conduct would be acceptable by a respected body of opinion.⁶⁹

6.0 “BOLAM” AND THE CHANGE IN THE COURTS ATTITUDE

Over the years, several cases have emerged in which the *Bolam* principle has come to play. Various jurisdictions the world over have challenged the principle. Obviously, there seem to be issues with the total adherence to this principle because the court seems to have only become an arena where the doctors come to legalize their actions, omissions and opinions. The courts seem to have their hands tied and have very little to say on what actually constitutes medical negligence. This is why there has been unrest in adoption of or departure from the principle. Some adopted it, others have improved on it and yet others have altogether discarded it. Jurisdictions of England, Singapore, Malaysia and Australia have witnessed a highly of judicial activity in the area of medical negligence by virtue of which new attitudes and outlooks have emerged.

7.0 CRIMINAL LIABILITY IN MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE

A part from civil liability for negligence, it is necessary to draw attention to the fact that, a medical practitioner may also be held criminally liable if his negligence passed beyond a mere matter of compensation between the parties and showed such disregard for the life and safety of others as to amount to a crime against the state and conduct deserving punishment.⁷⁰ It has been stated, however, that the degree of negligence required is gross and not mere negligence.⁷¹ Thus, both the Criminal and Penal Code provide sanctions for criminal negligence.⁷²

⁶⁷ Crawford v Board of Governor of Charging Cross Hospital- The Times, 8 December, 1953.

⁶⁸ Whiteford V Hunter (1950) 94Sj 758.

⁶⁹ See also Defreitas V O, Brien (1995) 2 Med LR 155; Ahmadu V Essien (1994) 7 NWLR (pt 354) 91.

⁷⁰ Emir () 268.

⁷¹ Ibid.

⁷² Sections 303 and 343 of the Criminal Code.

It is clear from the above provisions that the criminal liability of a doctor or medical practitioner for negligent treatment of a patient is predicated on a breach of duty which the doctor or medical practitioner owes to patient. Where therefore, the degree of skill, care and competence required of a doctor or medical practitioner is not met in any particular case, a breach of duty which may amount to criminal liability arises⁷³.

However, care must be taken in imputing criminal liability on the medical practitioners arbitrarily. This is because, more than civil litigations, criminal complaints that result in arrest of medical of a medical practitioner by the police are demoralizing⁷⁴.

As **Diana Kloss** pointed out ⁷⁵ medical practitioners and their regulatory bodies are not concerned only with injury to their pockets' the damage to reputation- that of the doctor personally and the medical profession generally- is probably a greater threat. *Ferner*,⁷⁶ for most errors... the criminal law is unsatisfactory. Convicting doctors of manslaughter may satisfy a desire for retribution, but deters careful consideration of the ways of preventing of the ways of preventing tragedies from recurring". Therefore, the fact that a life has been lost or that some person sustained an injury should lead to a presumption of rash or negligent act.

In conclusion, it is clear therefore the courts are treating histology and ultrasound scan cases similar in terms of the test used for breach- and it is not classic **Bolam**. The United States of America has the highest vibrant number of litigation in respect to medical negligence while the English jurisdiction exhibits a conservative approach to malpractice.⁷⁷ The English assumes a generally protective attitude to the medical profession with the believe that its position well reduced incidence of combative practice but invariably increases and the cost of health care. **In Yelen Kun-Yeu v. Alivof Hong Kong**⁷⁸, Lord Denning stated that in order to find a doctor liable for negligence his conduct should be deserving of censure or be inexcusable in the circumstance in other word, this means that the courts should be circumspect to find or rarely should find negligence against a doctor.

⁷³ *ibid*

⁷⁴ See ;Siemograph Services Ltd&Lords v mark(1993)7NWLR(pt304)203

⁷⁵ Kloss D .Perspectives in NHS Management : The Duty of Care: Medical Negligence, British Medical Journal,Vol.289.(1984)66

⁷⁶ Ferner R E. Medication Errors That Have Led To Manslaughter Charges, British Medical Journal Vol.321(2000)1212-1216.

⁷⁷ Emiri () 268.

⁷⁸ (1987)2AllER705.

8.0 RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Consolidation of Regulatory Frameworks: medical regulatory bodies should enhance their oversight functions. Regular reviews and updates of medical laws and guidelines should be made.
2. Review of the Bolam principle: The principle established case of should be reassessed to incorporate modern medical advancements and patient safety considerations.
3. Education and Advocacy: The general public should be educated about their rights and the standards of medical care they should accept. Advocacy groups can play a crucial role to that effect.
4. Medico-Legal Collaboration: Legal and medical professionals should collaborate closely to develop frameworks that ensure both accountability and support for medical legal practitioners. This could involve joint seminars, conferences, and writing like this one.
5. General Governmental Reforms: Governments should consider policy reforms that provide clear distinctions between Civil and Criminal negligence in medical practice. This includes setting clear parameters for when a case of medical negligence should escalate to a Criminal charge.

9.0 CONCLUSION

This article has provided an exposition of medical negligence, with particular emphasis on Civil and Criminal liabilities that may fall medical practitioners. It has among other things highlighted the key elements of negligence (i.e. duty of care, breach of duty and damage) within the context of medical practice. This article has shed light of the relationship between legal and medical practices with attention paid to difference in judicial approaches across different jurisdictions.

On a final note, the article discussed “the Bolam principle” demonstrating its significant role in determining the standard of care.